

Improving Health Insights by Standardising Australia's Healthcare Data

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The Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) is working across Australia with universities, government and health services to implement a shared data model enabling system-wide analytics and research.

How Can We Make the Most of Australia's Healthcare Data?

Australia's healthcare data holds untapped potential. Hospital and administrative health care records contain useful information on medical conditions, diagnostic tests, treatments, outcomes and patient demographics. This data can help reveal disease patterns, assess treatment effectiveness, and inform clinical guidelines to improve patient care. However, differences in how healthcare data are collected, recorded and stored across Australia make it difficult to compare and analyse.

What is the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model (OMOP CDM)?

The international gold standard for standardising health data. The OMOP Common Data Model standardises healthcare data into a consistent format. Developed by the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) initiative, the OMOP CDM enables data from different healthcare sites or jurisdictions to be more easily analysed and compared, without compromising security or patient confidentiality.

Used in more than 80 countries worldwide

Used to standardise more than 128 million unique patient records

Backed by \$12.3 million co-investment in Australia

Learn More

Learn how your organisation can implement the OMOP CDM.

Visit the AHDEN project

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Why Use The OMOP CDM?

Maximise the Value of Health Data: Standardising healthcare data enables seamless analysis across Australian jurisdictions, helping answer national questions about the safety, quality and innovation of healthcare.

Maintain Data Privacy and Security: Data custodians retain local governance and control, with patient-level data remaining secure behind local firewalls, while only de-identified summary statistics are shared for analysis.

Improve Scientific Rigour: Standardised data allow researchers to combine information from multiple sources, enabling them to conduct larger-scale analyses with greater confidence in the results.

Reduce Cost and Effort: Using a consistent format between different institutions reduces the need for time- and resource-intensive data wrangling.

Foster Collaboration: Because the OMOP CDM is used worldwide, it enables researchers to collaborate on international studies.

National Initiatives to Implement the OMOP CDM

The ARDC is partnering with universities, government and health services to implement the OMOP CDM through its People Research Data Commons (People RDC), which is delivering national scale data infrastructure for health research and translation.

A National Initiative to Transform Australia's Hospital Data

The OMOP CDM will be deployed across Australian hospitals by the **Australian Health Data Evidence Network (AHDEN)**, through a 3-year national initiative. AHDEN is led by Professor Nicole Pratt (project lead), Adelaide University, and President of OHDSI Australia. It's a national partnership between ARDC, Adelaide University and The University of Queensland, with more partners to be announced soon.

Standardising Australia's Admitted Patient Care (APC) Hospital Data

In another project, the Australian Institute of Health and Welfare is partnering with the ARDC to **standardise Australia's Admitted Patient Care (APC)** hospital data to a common language for both government agencies and external researchers by converting it to the OMOP CDM. This conversion will establish an interoperable national digital health asset that removes technical bottlenecks for researchers and analysts, speeds up medical breakthroughs, and enables Australian participation in worldwide health studies.

Enhancing Person Level Integrated Data Asset (PLIDA) for Health Research

A pilot project within this initiative, a partnership between the Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS) and ARDC, will implement the OMOP CDM and analytic tools within ABS secure research environment to demonstrate the feasibility of consistent large-scale observational health research and alignment with international standards.

The OMOP CDM in Action

Most medications rely on randomised clinical trials to test their safety and efficacy before they are approved for broader public use. However, clinical trials are often conducted on a small scale, making it difficult to detect rare and severe side effects that may only be visible at the population level. The OMOP CDM standardises health data so researchers can compare datasets from around Australia and the world to use in large-scale studies, helping identify rare adverse effects and draw more robust conclusions. Researchers have already used the OMOP CDM to help investigate the safety and effectiveness of medicines for heart failure, cardiovascular disease and asthma. The tool will also help the healthcare system respond more rapidly to major health threats such as future pandemics

When COVID-19 emerged in 2020, Australia's healthcare data was not harmonised, unlike some other countries such as South Korea. This made it difficult to get an accurate picture of how the virus was spreading across the country and the effectiveness of treatments and vaccines, especially in vulnerable people. Once the AHDEN initiative is implemented, we will be able to identify and respond to future pandemics and major health threats much faster.

Professor Nicole Pratt, President of OHDSI Australia, Adelaide University

How Does the OMOP CDM Work?

The OMOP CDM transforms disparate data into a common format by using standard vocabularies, terminologies and coding schemes. The model can be implemented and used within existing database infrastructure, without the data ever leaving its host institution. Once in a common format, the database can be used to generate rigorous and reproducible evidence using standardised analytics tools.

About the ARDC

At the ARDC, we drive the development of world-class national digital research infrastructure, enhancing research impact and giving Australian researchers a competitive advantage through access to comprehensive and high-quality data.

The ARDC is enabled by the Australian Government's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

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CONTACT ardc.edu.au
 +61 3 9902 0585
 contact@ardc.edu.au

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